

PACIFICUS

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- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“MADNESS IN PLAIN CLOTHES”

Am I crazy? Is this a fractured mind?
I commit mistakes but little you find.
Is this because of my upbringing?
No! I guess it is the peer pressure thing.

But what do you think can constitute crime?
When all I know I only enjoyed those rum and lime.
Am I too young to understand things like that?
Maybe unkissed by truth, I hurt your gut.

The statute makers made sure I live by writ,
Yet why do I always choose society's expectations unmet?
Mentally ill? Who isn't? Call me bitter.
But for me, we all are a little crazy,
It's just that the ones outside asylums hide it a little better.

